

REDI4HEAT

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

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PROJECT PARTNERS

ADENE: Agencia para a Energia

BIO: Bioenergy Europe

CRES: Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving Foundation

DENA: Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH

EGEC: European Geothermal Energy Council

EHP: Euroheat & Power

EHPA: European Heat Pump Association

EIHP: Energetski Institut Hrvoje Pozar

SHE: Solar Heat Europe / European Solar Thermal Industry Federation

ENC: Energy Cities

KAPE: Krajowa Agencja Poszanowania Energii Spolka Akcyjna

TRI: Trinomics BV

ABBREVIATION AND ACRONYMS

REDI4HEAT: RED implementation for heating and cooling

C&D: Communication and Dissemination

RHC: Renewable Heating and Cooling

H&C: Heating and Cooling

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project description and main objectives

Heating and cooling represent 50% of the energy demand in Europe and 80% of the energy consumption in households. The decarbonization of heating and cooling is essential to the decarbonization of our energy sector. It is a major challenge that needs to be addressed urgently. The Clean Energy Package introduced several measures aiming at increasing considerably the uptake of renewable heating and cooling solutions by 2030. Most Member States have yet to design strategies for the heating and cooling sector that are ambitious and effective enough in order to comply with the Renewables Directive, namely Article 23. REDI4HEAT aims to support the implementation of the RED provisions on heating and cooling as well as to assist Member States and local authorities in that process. The project will provide a better understanding of the shortcoming in current strategies and propose to address these with a set of recommendations, which shall include Strategic Policy Priorities for heating and cooling, Policy adoption scenarios, best practices, among others.

This deliverable D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan aims at presenting a comprehensive, impact-driven, Communication and dissemination strategy focused on raising awareness of the general public and the stakeholders, through the promotion of the achievements and gained knowledge of the project.

The strategy is prepared at an early stage of the project (M7), and throughout the project progress is foreseen to be updated on a regular basis.

The plan has been developed in relation to the project proposal, the project Grant Agreement, EHPA's experience in communication and dissemination of EU projects and the general guidelines contained in the documents below:

- “Communicating research for evidence-based policy-making – A practical guide for researchers in socio-economic sciences and humanities” ([European Commission, 2011](#))
- “Communicating EU Research & Innovation: A guide for project participants” ([European Commission, 2012](#)).

1.2 Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination strategy

The Communication and Dissemination Plan aims at providing a clear overview on how all the communication channels and activities will work together to address the identified stakeholder groups as well as to raise their awareness in the development of the project outcomes.

The Plan explains the methodology that will be followed by the consortium as to ensure the visibility of the REDI4HEAT project, the involvement of the stakeholders, as well as the maximization of the project impacts. The activities included in the Plan will be discussed and updated on a regular basis to ensure that the developments of the project are accessible and the main messages are communicated and are disseminated in a consistent manner.

EHPA is the Leader of the Work Package 6 Dissemination, Communication & Networking and will coordinate the implementation of the activities described in this strategic document. It has to be noted that the successful implementation of these activities can only be achieved with the cooperation and commitment of all project partners.

WP6 plays a vital role in raising awareness on renewable heating and cooling, fostering interaction with key stakeholders and supporting partners in effectively achieving their communicative objectives within the project.

WP6 also takes the lead on translating the most technical findings into a more tangible form so as to ensure that the project's communication and dissemination resonates with different types of audiences.

The workplan will be divided into two main areas:

1. Communication activities: focused on promoting the activities of the project and raising awareness on renewable heating and cooling to a general audience, including decision makers.
2. Dissemination activities: focused on spreading the results obtained to the identified target groups and to foster opportunities for collaboration with other related projects.

The overall objectives of this strategy are:

- To disseminate REDI4HEAT's outputs through diverse channels and to adapt technical language into messages understandable by different audiences.
- To raise awareness on renewable heating and cooling at European, National, Regional and local level.
- To facilitate regular flows of information within the consortium as well as to ensure that partners can effectively communicate and disseminate their work in a coherent and harmonized way, ensuring a common message from the REDI4HEAT project.
- To contribute to exchanges of information and experiences between organisations and to enable partners receiving regular updates on the work carried out.

- To inform and raise awareness about the progress of REDI4HEAT by disseminating the project's generated knowledge among relevant stakeholders at EU, national and local levels.
- To motivate the different targeted stakeholders to be involved in the project, and participate in the project results.
- To educate and influence relevant stakeholders with the goal of having an impact on the RED provisions on heating and cooling.

1.3 Stakeholder Analysis

The communication and dissemination strategy cannot be separated from a clear stakeholder analysis. The dissemination method is based on a stakeholder mapping that has been conducted within the REDI4HEAT Consortium. The mapping process, whose first results are identified in this section, has determined the needs and characteristics of the audience thus allowing the identification of effective messages and communication tools to successfully reach the target groups.

This analysis provides valuable insights on the “rationale to engage” and “incentives to engage” of the different stakeholder groups and facilitates the dissemination process by using relevant and integrated communication tools aimed at ensuring REDI4HEAT's success. In order to guarantee that the dissemination strategy is relevant, the effectiveness of the stakeholder analysis is monitored throughout the whole duration of the project.

This section of the C&D plan is based on a thorough assessment of the target groups that REDI4HEAT addresses. In M3, a survey was circulated within the Consortium to identify the main stakeholder needs at local, national and EU levels. The stakeholder analysis is based on the responses of 9 REDI4HEAT Partners representing both the national (3) and European (6) levels.

The segmentation of the project's target audience was done according to the stakeholders' profile. The primary target group of this project are **policy and decision makers** concerned with the drafting, approval and implementation of support tools on renewable energy sources. A secondary target group is represented by **heating and cooling companies, trade associations and consumer groups**. The third target group is composed of those **experts** who have a strategic role in the discussion on renewable heating and cooling. A fourth relevant group to address is made of **media, NGOs** and other players, eg. Think tanks, important in terms of dissemination of information about RHC potential and related policies and support mechanisms. Finally, **International and European organisations** active in the field of renewable energies will be addressed and initiatives will be organised in synergy with the priorities sought by these entities.

A close examination of the surveys' results showed that in terms of stakeholders' needs and best communication strategies/messages the differences between EU, national and local levels are minor. For this reason, the stakeholders analysis below reports the survey's result based on the profile and

area of work of the afore-mentioned target groups without taking much into account their geographical segmentation.

Although not specifically addressed by this deliverable, each partner is still responsible to readapt the project messages according to the specific needs of the audience they interact with each time. Trying to systematise such varied and extremely diverse needs in a table would be a pointless exercise at this stage and it has been considered more appropriate to only assess the most common needs of the main target groups according to their area of expertise and working category, as follows:

- Policy makers
- Industry representatives
- Experts on H&C
- Media/Think tanks/NGOs addressing energy related topics
- International Organisations addressing energy related topics

The aim of this assessment is to elaborate a more effective communication and dissemination strategy that could be easily adaptable to the different target groups' needs and interests, thus maximising the potential impact and value of the project.

The first section of the survey addressed the project-relevant communication challenges and needs of the key stakeholders. The answers provided by the eight respondents are summarised in the following table.

Stakeholders' profile	Relevant needs for the stakeholder group	Relevant communication challenges for the project in relation to each stakeholder group addressed
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of awareness about RHC technologies (their potential, cost effectiveness, efficiency, environmental impact, security); - Need to overcome the idea of “silver bullet” political solutions in the implementation of renewable energy options; - Need to exchange know-how on existing policies for the heating and cooling sector with other relevant actors. - Lack of multilevel dialogues needed to understand the reality of local authorities: lack of skilled staff at policy level and lack of empowerment to act and implement relevant measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visibility: ability to stand out from other policy-related RHC projects - To shift policy makers' attention from the power sector to H&C - Raise awareness at every geographical level about the importance of H&C decarbonisation and H&C technologies (Heat is a local issue but it has to be tackled at EU level).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At national level, need for ministries to include RHC issues as well as the outcomes of REDI4HEAT (deliverables and tools) in NECPs. 	
Industry representatives (from trade associations and companies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to have effective communication channels with other relevant actors to facilitate the introduction of renewables in the H&C sector; - Need to learn about RHC best practices to replicate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Address financial and economic aspects related to RHC to attract industry representatives - Provide information on the impact of RED updates on the enterprises
Experts on Heating and Cooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to learn about RHC most innovative solutions, market trends, new technologies and their competitiveness - Need to see RHC research put into practice - Need to familiarize with policy/market uptake issues - Need to make their solutions and related benefits understandable by the general public and policy makers - Need to adapt new technologies to local realities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop new research and solutions specific enough to address their interests - To attract stakeholders' attention around RHC technological solutions - To create a link between experts and other relevant actors in the H&C sector so to implement what has been studied - Translate complex technical knowledge in simple/ready to use information for the general public and for the project target groups - Provide useful resources and training material to local experts (public administration, energy agencies...) - Provide information on the impact of RED updates at EU and National levels
Media, Think Tanks and NGOs addressing topics related to energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to get insights on existing RHC policies and work on new solutions to be implemented by relevant actors in the field - General lack of holistic knowledge of the H&C sector (technologies, socio-economic benefits, environmental impact, potential, competitiveness, market data) - Need to adapt solutions to the local reality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide new research inputs and solutions specific enough to address their interests - Communicate the potential and benefits of RHC technologies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to know the implications of anticipated changes for businesses, residents, energy communities and the effects of the RED updates 	
International organisations (IEA, IRENA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to learn the potential and benefits of RHC and the latest developments - Need to empower the local level for more effective action 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To shift their attention from the power to the heating and cooling sector by showcasing H&C technologies and markets and offering the same visibility to all RES solutions

As presented in the table, the stakeholders in the H&C sector have different needs and communication challenges. Policy makers need to increase awareness of Renewable Heating and Cooling (RHC) technologies, overcome the idea of "silver bullet" solutions, and engage in multilevel dialogues. Industry representatives need effective communication channels and information on financial and economic aspects related to RHC. Experts in H&C need to learn about RHC solutions, see their research put into practice, and translate technical knowledge for the general public and policy makers. Think tanks and NGOs lack holistic knowledge of the H&C sector and need to adapt solutions to the local reality. International organisations need to learn about the potential and benefits of RHC and empower local levels for more effective action.

For what concerns the communication challenges, these focus mainly on understanding how to raise awareness on the importance of H&C decarbonisation and shifting the interest from power sector to H&C and making RHC solutions understandable and visible to all.

2. EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

2.1 Language

The language of this project is English. For purposes of consistency, adherence to British English spelling conventions is recommended. In order to avoid unnecessary editorial work at later stages, the guidelines in the [EC English Style Guide](#) can be followed.

Any material targeting NSGs, national agencies and local authorities can be translated into the national languages of the countries addressed as well, if deemed necessary by the Consortium.

2.2 Key messages and communication tools

The general key message of REDI4HEAT will play on the wording of the project title, which sounds like “Ready for heat”. The project name itself conveys a positive idea of being ready for the renewable heating and cooling transition and it invites the audience to make this green change happen. REDI4HEAT also refers to the Renewable Energy Directive whose implementation the project wants to support. Secondary messages will be developed and used, when appropriate, together with the main message. These messages will respect the specificity of each communication channel, and the profile and needs of the stakeholder groups as described in section 1.3.

The second part of the Survey that was circulated among the consortium in M3 aimed at investigating ad hoc key messages and best communication strategies and tools that the project should adopt based on the type of stakeholders’ profile. The following table sums up its findings.

Stakeholders’ profile	Key messages	Best Communication Strategies and Tools
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “We cannot do it without heating and cooling – 50% of EU energy consumption” - “We have effective solutions with high potential needing more policy support” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Targeted bilateral meetings - Policy workshops invitin - Case studies - Factsheets - Social media - Articles - Networking opportunities during events - Online seminars - Cooperation with sector unions
Industry representatives (from trade associations and companies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong messages underlining that “70 percent of CO2 in industry comes from process heat” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices and case studies - Workshops - Relevant EU fairs on HVAC - Analysis
Experts on Heating and Cooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Others have done so why not you? - Together we are stronger 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateral meetings with relevant actors; - Capacity building sessions - Factsheets - Reports - Best practices - Workshops/Events (invite the mas speakers) - Email campaign
Think Tanks and NGOs addressing topics related to energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on the potential and benefits of H&C technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices - Bilateral meetings with relevant actors; - Factsheets - Workshops (invite them as speakers) - Articles - Social Media/Website - Visual communication (videos)

International organisations (IEA, IRENA)	- Focus on the potential and benefits of H&C technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews - Targeted meetings - Scientific and technical articles - Factsheets - Workshops and events - Case studies
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As reported in the table, overall the recommended communication strategies and tools for all stakeholders include a mix of targeted meetings, workshops, case studies, factsheets, and online and social media channels. By using these tools and emphasising the importance of H&C technologies, stakeholders can help promote their use in the European Union.

In the specific, the key message to address policy makers should focus on relevant data, such as the following *“H&C is critical and constitutes 50% of EU energy consumption”*, also the one provided for industry representatives should focus on real percentage like *“70% of CO2 in industry comes from process heat”* because it highlights the urgency of the problem and the impact it generates. To address the experts on H&C, a good message should focus on the need of acting together, highlighting what others have done, to try to involve always more person in contributing to the action. While the message for think tanks, NGOs addressing energy and international organisations should focus on the potential and benefits of H&C technologies; in this way they could help to promote their use and encourage the development of more efficient and sustainable solutions.

REDI4HEAT secondary messages will be based on the previous list, which can be subject to further additions and/or changes throughout the whole project lifecycle.

Apart from the material published on the project website, REDI4HEAT foresees to reach the public through a combination of different tools that, thanks to their variety and different features, are going to effectively reach and inform the whole range of stakeholders: from the most critical ones to the less interested parties.

The main C&D tools, to be further explored in the following sections will be: the project visual identity, website, social media pages and posts, flyers, press releases, policy briefs, newsletters, webinars, publications, participation to fairs and conferences.

2.3 Visual Identity: templates, logo and disclaimer

During the first months of the project (by M6) a common visual identity will be developed so as to ensure an immediate recognition of the project.

The logo of REDI4HEAT will be used in all templates, reports and dissemination activities throughout the project.

The REDI4HEAT logo was officially crafted during the proposal stage and accordingly adapted at the start of the project following the indications of all the partners.

Based on the visual identity, approved by the partners of the consortium, templates for Microsoft Word, Microsoft PowerPoint and Microsoft Excel will be developed by EHPA (see in Annex).

These templates must be used by all the partners during the course of the project for their presentations, reports and other project material developed.

As included in REDI4HEAT's Grant Agreement, all the materials that are used in the Communication and Dissemination of the project must contain the EU Disclaimer. All partners are invited to use the following disclaimer (that can be translated into local languages when necessary) in: press releases, conferences, on site or online seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, and presentations.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, its agencies or granting authorities. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

2.4 Website

Within WP6, EHPA is leading the action on developing a new website for REDI4HEAT. This will be hosted on EHPA's website as a sub-domain. The decision of not creating a new domain for the website was taken by the Consortium during the project Kick-off meeting and it is aimed at reaching three main objectives:

- **To make the project more cost-effective:** creating a new domain requires more money than creating a sub-domain.
- **To increase the project's visibility** during its lifecycle: EHPA website already has a broad base of visitors. Having the project's website strictly linked to EHPA will more easily encourage the EHPA virtual audience to visit the REDI4HEAT webpage.
- **To guarantee the project's sustainability** after its completion: EHPA will be responsible for the project's maintenance for 8 years in total, so up to 5 years after the project's end.

A first version of the website will be ready by M5, open for comments from all Partners whereas the final version will be live by M6 (March 2023).

All information will be secure and will follow the General Data Protection Regulation. The website will also host the resources developed under the other Work Packages, where applicable. For example:

- All public project deliverables
- The Renewable Heat Transition Toolbox (T3.4)
- The Environmental Footprint calculator (M2)
- The knowledge sharing platform for national and local agencies (T4.2)
- The policy briefs resulting from WP5
- All news articles, press releases and (scientific/non-scientific) publications concerning the project as well as the promotional material and video recordings of the organized project webinars (T 6.3)
- The promotion and outcomes of the Project Final High-level event (T6.4)

The REDI4HEAT website will be the main communication and dissemination platform and it will allow stakeholders, end-users and the general public to have access to the project activities and results. It will promote relevant contents paying particular attention to the key stakeholder groups with the aim of engaging them in the conversation. The website will be a content generation tool where partners are going to be involved in developing content thus increasing the project visibility and maximizing its impact.

In brief, the key aims of the website can be reduced to three:

- a) Become the primary point of contact and information for REDI4HEAT: to explain about the project's aims, provide the latest news updates, provide reports and other public deliverables for download, and redirect to social media activity related to the project.
- b) To act as a more general hub for outcomes relevant to REDI4HEAT: to provide important updates on external policy/research developments that have an impact or are of interest to the project. This helps frame the project within a dynamic policy environment.
- c) To host/redirect to the knowledge-sharing platform for national and local agencies (to be developed and managed by ADENE, CREA and EHPA) that will act as a useful tool collecting REDI4HEAT resources but also previous and ongoing initiatives made available in an attractive and user-friendly environment. The resources encompass policies description, incentives schemes, national, regional and local strategies, training materials, simulation tools, and will be made available with a short assessment that presents the resource, the context and achievements and an adoption guideline.

The initial structure of the REDI4HEAT website will be as follows

- Home
- About
- Consortium
- News and Events
- Knowledge Sharing Centre
- Project Materials
 - Deliverables
 - Dissemination material
 - Policy briefs
 - Publications
 - Workshops and webinars
- Get Involved!
 - Sign up

- Contacts

The REDI4HEAT website will be promoted by all partners in various ways:

- All promotional material (leaflets and flyers) will include the link to the website (also under the form of QR code);
- Every partner will have to have a webpage on their own website dedicated to REDI4HEAT and redirecting visitors to the main website;
- The project social media pages will redirect followers to the website
- In all conferences and events the link to the website will be included in all dissemination material and presentations.

The website will be developed in English. Nonetheless short summaries in the national REI4HEAT languages will also be available to facilitate users engagement and redirect to the national partners that can provide more information.

2.5 Printed Promotional material

Once the REDI4HEAT visual identity has been defined, promotional material such as flyers and leaflets will be created and spread both in digital and printed formats.

In carrying out the dissemination activities, the consortium will adopt a green approach by minimising printed materials, using recycled paper (if necessary) and encouraging online communication. The REDI4HEAT flyers will be 'short and catchy' and they will have a light and portable format. The flyers will be first developed in English and then translated in all national languages of the 5 Member States involved. This will ensure a more effective dissemination of the project results also at local and national levels. The Flyer will include key information that would make readers curious about the project while providing brief information regarding REDI4HEAT objectives, Consortium and outcomes.

It will aim at attracting people's attention thus encouraging them to find out more about the project, its results and tools. The flyers will have a QR code that will redirect readers to the Project website and they will promote the project social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube). All Partners will need to add their input/comments on the contents of printed and digital flyers.

These will be used for dissemination and promotion purposes at external conferences, fairs, meetings and seminars. The leaflets will be circulated among all partners, they will be made available to download from the website and they will be updated during the project lifecycle. Partners are invited

to translate the relevant materials and make it available, in digital formats, in their own webpages and at the national section in the REDI4HEAT website.

2.6 E-newsletters

E-newsletters will ensure both communication and dissemination at different levels – national, EU and international – and will keep the stakeholders updated with the findings of the project, inform about other relevant events, publications, key policy developments, key messages of the project partners.

At least 5 newsletters in total are foreseen and they will address all relevant and interested stakeholder.

The aims of the newsletters are:

- Informing stakeholders on the key findings of the project;
- Providing information about relevant external and internal events thus encouraging participation;
- Promoting and redirecting readers to project-related scientific / non-scientific publications;
- Disseminating key messages from the project and main results
- Ensuring key stakeholders are kept up to date on key policy developments at EU level.

The e-newsletter will be distributed to the Consortium and to the REDI4HEAT newsletter subscribers via the website. The possibility to subscribe to the newsletter will also be promoted through the Project website and social media as well as shared by all partners with their networks.

The identity and formatting of the newsletter will be in-line with the pre-defined visual identity. The following is a proposed structure of each issue:

- Editorial feature – A feature article (roughly 200-350 words) item on a key topic, written by an expert.
- Supporting feature(s) – Supporting features of approx. 150-400 words on a topic related to the editorial, article sources can be external.

- REDI4HEAT Update – Where the project stands and what the next steps are. Provide an update of where the project stands (e.g. new milestones, deliverables, outputs and events) comprehensible to the newly subscribed.
- News & Events – Five to nine short items about relevant events and policy developments.
- Reading tips – Specially selected documents and research relevant to REDI4HEAT work suggested by WP leaders and all partners. Content to include title, author(s), link, and/or one-line synopsis.

The suggested schedule for the e-newsletter is the following:

- M7 – April 2023
- M15 – December 2023
- M22 – July 2024
- M29 – February 2025
- M36 – September 2025

Although it is not compulsory, project partners are invited to translate the e-newsletters, to use also as a communication opportunity in their own websites and media channels and also to make it available in the national sections of the REDI4HEAT website as a way to attract and provide information to non-proficient English readers.

2.7 Social-media channels

The project has three social media pages: one on LinkedIn, one on Twitter and one on Youtube. The pages have been created in M1 (October 2022) and some of them (LinkedIn and Twitter) have already been populated with some contents.

The stakeholder analysis is going to inform the content strategy, i.e. the typologies of content to use and the means and messages used to reach different types of audience at a local, national and european levels.

REDI4HEAT main themes that will represent the core-topics to be addressed in social media are: renewable heating and cooling, sustainable energy, decarbonisation, energy efficiency, energy optimization, solar thermal energy, geothermal energy, bioenergy, heat pump technology.

Potential categories related to the above-mentioned themes:

- About REDI4HEAT
- Outcomes – produced by REDI4HEAT and Partners
- Technologies
- Case studies
- Business models
- Policies
- Industry news
- Innovation
- Events / Webinars
- Multimedia

Twitter (<https://twitter.com/REDI4HEAT>) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/REDI4HEAT/>) will be the main social media channels to be used for the dissemination of REDI4HEAT's work because of their complementarity in addressing the stakeholder groups.

For an effective dissemination of REDI4HEAT in social media, it is vital for the partners to actively contribute to the published contents. Original content will lead to incremental reach and traffic for all social media channels, as well as the website.

An Excel sheet with three tables (see Annex I) has been shared among the Consortium in order to collect all events, publications and digital activity implemented by the partners and promote REDI4HEAT outcomes and impact. The Consortium inputs on these tables will both help to keep track of all the project dissemination activities carried out within the Consortium thus allowing such activities to be effectively and systematically promoted through REDI4HEAT social media channels.

2.8 Publications: Press releases and scientific publications

As per Grant Agreement, the Consortium will issue a minimum of three press releases throughout the whole duration of the project. The first press release has been issued in M1 to launch the project. During the General Assemblies the consortium will periodically decide they key points when press releases are more worth being published (on the occasion of a particularly important deliverable being submitted or before a special project event).

As a general rule, each partner may issue its own press release but should inform all other partners before sending it out in order to ensure accuracy and consistency of information. For every press release made mentioning REDI4HEAT, WP6 leader (EHPA) and the Coordinator (CRES) should be

informed; information collected will be used for reporting purposes and to ensure that all target groups and policy areas are effectively reached.

Press releases will be drafted and circulated to the relevant Work Package Leaders for review and comments. If the work of one of the partners is mentioned in the press release, the partner in question shall be informed and approve of its contents.

Each press release will carry a key message about the project's work, with the aim of generating interest about the project's activities in other organisations. In order to increase the number of readers reached, the articles will also be published on the REDI4HEAT website and partners will be invited to share them on their own webpage. When possible, partners are invited to translate the press releases and disseminate it through their media network and national information channels in their official language.

In addition, at least 2 open access publications in scientific journals are foreseen during the second half of the project.

Examples of relevant journals and publications include:

- Energy Conversion and Management,
- Applied Energy,
- Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews,
- Energy, International Journal of Refrigeration,
- International Journal of Control,
- Hydrocarbon Processing Magazine.

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1 Policy Briefs

Under Task 5.1, a series of policy briefs is foreseen to be published. The papers will be focusing on key measures in upcoming EU policies dealing with RHC legislation and NECPs. In addition a webinar targeting both EU and MS stakeholders will be organised to present these briefs and facilitate a debate on the new requirements.

This task will coordinate with WP3, so that the development of recommendations and tools for the deployment of RES-HC take into account the new requirements included in the new regulations.

The policy briefs will be written in a suitable format to clearly and effectively disseminate the project's messages. They will provide 'at glance' materials that outline all the learnings and recommendations of the project and will be delivered in a visually appealing format.

The policy briefs will be presented to national authorities during ad hoc meetings, taking in consideration the national context and translated them in the official language of each country, when is possible, to provide a more effective result.

Leaflets and informational fact sheets will be prepared throughout the project in a digital format in English (also available on the website) and in hard copy format for distribution during workshops, events and conferences, in order to encourage the dissemination of the policy contents also among the general public.

3.2 Participation in Conferences, Forums and Fairs

REDI4HEAT and its outcomes will be presented in several EU and international forums events as well as partner events related to the scope of the project in order to boost the Consortium's and the results visibility.

The Consortium will participate in at least 15 dissemination conferences/forums/fairs; some of the events identified for the REDI4HEAT project at an initial stage are:

- EUSEW – EU Sustainable Energy Week (20/06/2023 - 22/06/2023)
- WSED – World Sustainable Days (28/02/2023 - 03/03/2023)
- Energy Transition Forum Global Summit (23/03/2023)
- European Week of Regions and Cities (10/10/2023 – 13/10/2023)
- The Covenant of Mayors Investment Forum
- EHPA's Annual Heat Pump Forum (28/09/2023)
- IEA Heat Pump Conference (15/05/2023 – 18/05/2023)
- European Shallow Geothermal Days
- Sustainable Places (14/06/2023 – 16/06/2023)
- ISH Messe Frankfurt (13/03/2023 – 17/03/2013)
- Zero Emission Mediterranean (10/10/2023 - 12/10/2023)
- Clean Energy Summit (30/03/2023)
- EU Green Week (03/06/2023 – 11/06/2023)
- Smart City EXPO world Congress (07/11/2023 – 09/11/2023)

Each of the partners is encouraged to present the project at external events so as to widen the impact of the project. The coordinator CRES must be at all times informed beforehand about the planned presentations and the content they will display. The presentation content will be developed in cooperation with the coordinator, when necessary, to ensure consistency.

A document will be created to collect the dissemination activities of all the partners. The document must be filled every month by all partners so as to gather all the dissemination activities that have taken place throughout the project for reporting purposes as well as to monitor that all the target groups are effectively reached.

3.3 Webinars and Workshops

In order to further disseminate the project results, share the main updates of the policy packages and engage with new stakeholders, REDI4HEAT will organize a series of webinar and workshops. The webinars will be organized alongside sister projects (to be defined) and the workshops in cooperation with other work-packages.

The table below displays the original planning for those to take place, susceptible to change throughout the course of the project depending on the dissemination necessities.

When	Topic	WPS involved
17 May 2023 M8	REDI4HEAT webinar with sister projects	WP6
5 September 2023 M12	OW with public authorities to increase the understanding of RED and EED	WP2, WP5
M18	OW presenting the assessment of the NECPs, market barriers, and consumption trends	WP2
M21	REDI4HEAT webinar with sister projects	TBD
M24	OW sharing best practices and business models identified in some MS	WP3
M26	REDI4HEAT webinar with sister projects	TBD
M30	OW about the exploitation and replication of our project's results	WP7

3.4 Collaboration with other EU Projects

In the proposal stage, the Consortium foresaw that the REDI4HEAT project would have initiated collaborations with similar EU initiatives to encourage synergies and further enhance the dissemination of the achieved results. One of the purposes of the REDI4HEAT knowledge sharing centre (WP4) is to aggregate resources that are relevant for local and national authorities, which

means also making use of the outputs of different European projects. This collaboration will be addressed in particular in Task 5.3 aiming to investigate which tools to include in the REDI4HEAT toolbox. REDI4HEAT will use and upscale the results from other relevant projects to enable the development of recommendations and tools for the deployment of RES-HC and to support the implementation of effective support measures for RES-HC.

Some of the projects that were included in the proposal are still ongoing:

Project name	Framework Programme	Period of duration	Potential collaboration	Link
ODYSSEE-MURE “Energy Efficiency Trends & Policies”	LIFE-CET	October 2022 – March 2025	Complementarity between these projects will provide valuable input to the assessment of databases on energy efficiency indicators and energy consumption by end-users and their underlying drivers in industry, transport and buildings, databases on energy efficiency policies and measures by country in industry, transport and buildings as well as of tools for assessing energy efficiency progress and performance across countries and energy efficiency policy evaluation.	https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/
LOCOMOTION “Low-carbon society: an enhanced modelling tool for the transition to sustainability”	H2020	June 2019 – May 2023	The objective of LOCOMOTION is to enhance existing Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) in order to provide policy makers and relevant stakeholders with a reliable and practical model system to assess the feasibility, effectiveness, costs and impacts of different sustainability policy options and to identify the most effective transition pathways towards a low-carbon society. This new IAM will be a robust, usable and reliable tool of diagnostic and scenario assessment for a sustainable transition towards a low-carbon society.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/821105

In addition, the Consortium will look for opportunities of cooperation also with other projects and initiatives that were successfully selected under similar calls of LIFE and Horizon Europe Programmes such as:

Project name	Framework Programme	Period of duration	Potential collaboration	Link
GEOBOOST	LIFE CET	2023-2025	Policies and regulations on geothermal HP	soon

3.5 Meetings with Policy Makers

Under Task 6.3, to pursue the goal of disseminating the project's results, sharing the main updates of the policy packages, and engaging with new stakeholders, the Consortium is required to organize at least 10 meetings with policymakers, experts in the Heating and Cooling sector. EHPA is coordinating this task, but every partner is requested to collaborate and contribute to the realisation of these activities.

To organize the policy makers meetings, each Consortium partner is encouraged to search for and propose contact of policy makers, expert in the topics of Heat and Cooling, they would like to invite to take part to these meetings and to stay in constant contact with policy makers at EU level, as well a National and Regional via their membership base.

These meetings are an important occasion to develop dissemination tasks and present the on-going activities, the results achieved until that moment by the project and to keep informed the audience about the planned next steps; these meetings can be also an opportunity to exchange the main updates of the policy packages and engage with new stakeholders.

3.6 High-level Event

In month 36, a high-level event on renewable heating and cooling will be organised to bring together stakeholders from all relevant fields and to share REDI4HEAT results, achieved objectives and impact. Thought leaders and experts on renewable heating and cooling and decision-makers at a European and national level will be invited.

The final conference will be held onsite, in Brussels, and will address experts, energy managers, researchers and policy makers wishing to be informed of the project outcomes and impact. The event will be an opportunity to present all the outcomes produced in three years of activity and it will be one more occasion to network and create synergies with similar initiatives, thus encouraging the sustainability of the project results and their transferability to other contexts.

150 people are foreseen to take part to the conference both onsite and online. The conference will be indeed live streamed to increase the visibility of project results. A broad audience will be stimulated through multi-media and online tools.

The content and branding of the final conference will be developed and finalized in close collaboration with all the partners.

3.7 Collaboration with other REDI4HEAT WPs

Work package 6 is transversal to all the other WPs as it needs to communicate and disseminate all the activities implemented and results achieved within the other WPs to the general public and among the target groups.

Nevertheless, based on the nature of their activities, some WPs require a stricter collaboration with WP6 than others. For example, the knowledge-sharing platform for national and local agencies developed under T4.2 will need to be linked with the project website; in order to be helpful to the addressed target groups, this platform needs to be developed in close cooperation with the project website and properly promoted on social media and other channels so to attract the main stakeholders' attention.

Within WP4, also T4.3 activities will have to be carried out in collaboration with WP6; T4.3 concerns the organization of capacity building events that will be based on an efficient communication of the project's results. The events organized will be promoted throughout website, social media account and newsletters.

Another part of the project that will require an intense collaboration with Work Package 6 concerns its sustainability, replication and exploitation, that are ensured by WP7. As per grant agreement, the Communication & Dissemination strategy and the Sustainability & exploitation one will have to be developed in close cooperation with each other in order to guarantee a coherent plan on how to present the project to the external audience.

3.8 Collaboration between WP6 & WP7

WP6 (coordinated by EHPA) and WP7 (coordinated by ADENE) are strictly linked to each other's and for this reason a particular collaboration is foreseen among them.

The main points of collaboration between the two WPs focus on:

- ensuring that all the deliverables of the projects will be public and accessible via the REDI4HEAT website and kept online upon the project's end: this will be done through their publication on the website of the project, ensuring that they are communicated in an attractive and user-friendly manner, characteristics that will facilitate the exploitation work part;
- High level meetings with policy makers, namely at European and national, ensuring that the partners have the necessary support to present the project results in a clear and engaging way to the relevant agents;
- Participation in sectoral events, related to H&C policies, what should be clearly coordinated not only between ADENE and EHPA, but also with all the partners
- Mapping of related partnerships and projects with whom to discuss synergies

The replication part in WP7 is focused on upscaling the project results and extend them beyond the project countries, through the organization of 3 online webinars in non-participatory countries; to organize them, ADENE needs to be aware of which are the countries really interested in being involved in the webinar and which ones are following the project. EHPA will provide information to ADENE about it, by tracking and studying analytics data (i.e., finding the non-participatory countries with the highest n° of signing up to the newsletter; highest n° of newsletter's views, highest website's views...)

Another point of collaboration between WP6 and WP7 is in the context of Heating and Cooling sector events, because the action of communication and dissemination of the results of these events is essential to conducting exploitation activity.

Lastly, considering the KPIs inserted in the C&D Plan, those require a continue monitoring and confrontation by ADENE and at the same time, EHPA will commit to supervise the KPIs inserted in the SE&R plan.

In general, a total alignment between WP6 and WP7 activities is fundamental to guarantee that the REDI4HEAT's communication and dissemination activities boost the replication and exploitation capacity of WP7, thus ensuring an overall benefit for the project.

4 Communication and dissemination monitoring

Channel	KPIs
Website	Number of visitors: > 1.000 on 2nd year > 3.000 on 3rd year Average visit duration > 2 min Number of downloads of resources >500 Number of online dissemination actions (posts, articles, new resources, etc.) >100
Brochure/leaflet	Distribution: <500 e-copies = Poor; 500-1000 e-copies = Good; >1000 e-copies = Excellent
Social media	At least 200 followers attracted and engaged
Press Releases	At least 3 published
Conferences, fairs, events	At least 3 per year
Workshops	At least 5 workshops at national level (1 per MS) with at least 50 participants
Networking activities	5 study tours at national level (1 per MS) with at least 20 participants 15 capacity building events with national, regional and local focus (3 per MS) with at least 30 participants

Webinars	3 online seminars with sister projects with at least 50 participants each 4 online workshops with at least 40 participants each
Newsletter	5 issues
Scientific publications	At least 2 in open access journals

4. Internal Communication

Internal communication is key to guarantee good communication among partners as well as ease the exchange of ideas and the interaction between work packages. Internal communication is a vessel to ensure a proper execution of the project to maximize its results.

The main tools used by partners for periodic communication will be:

- Teams: managed by EHPA, it is the tool selected for the exchange of documents, results and for facilitating collaboration. It is also the main tool to host video-calls among the different partners
- Emails: it is the tool chosen to exchange information among partners.

The members of the consortium will have the opportunity to communicate via:

- General Assembly: held twice a year physically in Brussels. All partners must participate as they are the place to update the whole consortium about the status of the project and discuss the upcoming steps.
- Steering Committees: take place periodically
- Work Package Meetings: held depending on the needs of every Work Package. The Work Package leader decides whether to have meetings with the partners involved

The involvement of all partners is vital for a successful dissemination of the project. Partners can support dissemination by:

- Circulating project materials (such as flyers and reports) to colleagues or potential interested parties.
- Presenting the project at conferences and other events and sharing the presentations used with the consortium
- Inviting potential interested parties to follow the project on social media
- Using their organization's communication tools to support the dissemination of the project (website, social media accounts)
- Linking the project's website to their own websites
- Keeping records of all their dissemination activities as they will be needed for reporting purposes

